

PROTOTYPING A WIRELESS INTEGRATED WEARABLE INTERACTIVE MUSIC SYSTEM: MUSFIT

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the development of a wireless integrated wearable interactive music system - Musfit. The system was built according to the intention of integrating the motion of hands (fingers), head, and feet of a performer to music performance. The device of the system consists of a pair of gloves, a pair of shoes, and a cap, which were embedded with various sensors to detect the body motion of a performer. The data from detecting was transmitted to a computer via a wireless device and then mapped into various parameters of sound effectors built on Max/MSP for interactive music performance.

The ultimate goal of the system is to free the performing space of the player, to increase technological transparency of performing and, as a result, to promote the interests of interactive music performance.

At the present stage, the progression of prototyping a wireless integrated wearable interactive music system has reached the goal we expected. Further studies are needed in order to assess and improve playability and stability of the system, in such a way that it can be effectively employed in concerts eventually.

1. INTRODUCTION

Wearable devices with sensors embedded have been widely adopted in human-computer interaction and new interfaces for musical expression communities [1]. A wireless wearable interactive music device controlled by body posture has been increasingly developed. A known example of wireless wearable devices for interactive music performance is Laetitia Sonami's Lady's Glove built and developed by Stein [2].

Different from Lady's Glove, the wireless wearable interactive music system - Musfit was intended to integrate the motion of hands (fingers), head, and feet of a performer to music performance.

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The device of the system consists of a pair of gloves, a pair of shoes, and a cap. Several hardware including Arduino [3], Bluetooth, and various sensors were employed in the system. Sensors built in gloves, shoes, and a cap, were used to detect the motion of performer's feet, fingers, and head.

The data from detecting was transmitted into a computer via a Bluetooth device and was mapped into various parameters of sound effectors via the algorithms of Max program. In addition, the mapped numbers were also used to trigger the mode switch of sound effectors or to trigger the mode of sound diffusion.

The object of the research is to prototype a wireless integrated wearable interactive music system, which could free the performing space of the player and increase the technological transparency of performance while involving the use of technologies in music concert. Figure 1 shows the prototyped wireless integrated wearable interactive music system - Musfit.

Figure 1. Musfit, a prototyped wireless integrated wearable interactive music system

2. STRUCTURE OF SYSTEM

In this section, the structure of interactive music system, structure of hardware and structure of software are described.

2.1 Structure of Interactive Music System

In the system, sensors built in the cap, gloves and shoes will detect performer's body motion. Sensor data from motion detection was transmitted into computer and was mapped into various parameters of sound effectors via algorithms of Max/MSP to transform the performer's voice collected from microphone. In addition, the data was also used to trigger the mode of sound effectors or mode of sound diffusion in a music performance.

For a performer, Musfit allows performer interacts with the system by body motion in real time to achieve her/his desired sounds or music results. For audience, the association of audio output from speakers and visual element from watching the body motion of the performer promotes the interests of appreciation of an interactive music performance. Figure 2 shows the overall structure of Musfit.

Figure 2. Overall structure of Musfit.

2.2 Structure of Hardware System

The hardware of the system was built on Arduino Nano. The PCB was employed to integrate the power supply, Arduino, Bluetooth, and various sensors. Figure 3 shows the structure of hardware of Musfit. Figure 4 shows the assembly of various hardware inside the gloves (same as those in shoes and cap)

Figure 3. Structure of hardware system of Musfit.

Figure 4. Assembly of hardware inside the glove.

Based upon the structure of hardware, sensor data from the body motion detection was converted into digits by Arduino, which were then transmitted into computer via Bluetooth device. Figure 5 shows the flow of data in the hardware system.

Figure 5. Flow of data in hardware system.

2.3 Structure of Software System

The software used for the interactive music system was based on the object-oriented music program-Max/MSP. The structure of software system consists of three main sections:

1. Input Section, which receives the Audio Source from microphone and Bluetooth parameters from serial port.
2. Signal Process Section, which consists of 2 sets of sound effectors: FX1 (ORI (Original), RM (Ring Modulation), and HARM (Harmonization)) and FX2 (Gran (Granular Synthesis), REV (Reverb), and FB (Feedback)). Those effectors process or modulate the input sound source according the dada received from Bluetooth.
3. Signal Output Section, which consists of 2 modes of sound output- stereo and 4-channel. Figure 6 shows the structure of software system of Musfit.

Figure 6. Structure of software system of Musfit.

3. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENT

In this section, the design and implementation of the device, including the cap, the gloves, and the shoes, and of software programming of the system are described.

3.1 Device

The electric compass was built on the brim of a cap to detect the motion angles of head. Figure 7 shows the installation of GY-273 electric compass on a cap.

Figure 7. GY-273 electric compass on a cap.

Three bend sensors were built on index, middle, and ring fingers of each glove to detect the bending degree of fingers. Figure 8 shows the installation of bend sensors in the gloves on index, middle, and ring fingers as indicated by arrows.

Figure 8. Bend sensors on fingers of a glove.

Pressure sensors were built in the front and rear insoles of shoes to detect the weights of feet stepping. Figure 9 shows the installation of pressure sensors on an insole.

Figure 9. Pressure sensors on an insole.

3.2 Software Programming

In the following texts, the design and implementation of the software programming are described.

3.2.1 Main User Interface

For a wearable music performance, a user friendly interactive interface is crucially needed to allow performer easily to monitor the change of parameters on screen and interact with the system to control the desired music results in real time.

Built on Max/MSP program environment, the main user interface of the system provides the performer four main sections of interactive information separated by different colors displayed in a presentation mode of the program. The information includes data information, audio information of left and right hand (including ORI, RM, Harm, Gran, Rev, and FB), select of sound effectors modular, and modes of sound output (either stereo or 4-channel). Figure 10 shows the main interactive interface of Musfit based on Max/MSP.

Figure 10. Main interactive interface of Musfit based on Max/MSP.

3.2.2 Sound Effector Modular Design

Since there were several sound effectors employed in the system, a design of preset of different sound effectors was also concerned. Sound effector modular allows performer to quickly select effector setting before the performance. Figure 11 shows the preset of sound effector modular of left hand.

Figure 11. Preset of sound effector modular of left hand.

4. MAPPING

The importance of mapping between gestures and sound is an active field of research [4] [5]. In this section, as shown on Table 1, the range settings and limits of sensors, the range of value for mapping, and the mapping associated with each part of the wearable device or motion of fingers, hand, and feet to various parameters of sound controls are described.

	Head (cap)	Hand (glove)	Feet (shoe)
Range settings and limits of sensors	Compass: North Gyroscope : 2 axes	Bending degree : 0~120	Weight range: 20g~2kg
Range of value	Heading : 0 ~ 360 X · Y : -360 ~ 360	0 ~ 1023	0 ~ 1023
Value to Sound Control Mapping	Spatilizati on of sound	Parameters of effectors	Mode switch of effectors and output channel

Table 1. Range of value and mapping of various values to sound controls.

4.1 Hand and Fingers (Gloves)

In the system, each hand was assigned to control different sound effectors. The left hand was assigned three types of sound effectors, including Original (without effect), Ring modulation, and Granular Synthesis. The right hand was assigned another three types of sound effectors, including Panning, Feedback, and Reverb. Figure 12 shows the assignments of controls of left and right hand.

Figure 12. Assignments of controls of left and right hand.

In the system, Fingers were used to control sound effectors via bend sensors built in the glove, which detect the bending degree (ranging from 0 to 120) of fingers. The data was converted into digits (ranging from 0 to 1023) by Arduino, and was then rescaled and mapped into parameters of effectors via algorithms of Max program.

Fingers of both hands play different roles in controlling. Fingers of left hand were used to control different parameters of various sound effectors. For example, index, middle, and ring finger were used to control the modular frequency, the carrier signal, and the output amount of signal of ring modulation respectively; index, middle, and ring finger were used to control the chord change, the carrier signal, and the output amount of signal of granular synthesis respectively. Table 2 shows the mapping of fingers to parameters of sound effectors.

Mode/Left	Finger	Description
Original	Non	Bypass original
Ring Modulation	Index	Modular frequency
	Middle	Carrier signal
	Ring	Signal amount
Granular synthesis	Index	Chord change
	Middle	Carrier signal
	Ring	Signal amount

Table 2. Mapping of fingers of left hand to parameters of sound effectors.

Giving more examples, index, middle, and ring finger of right hand were used to control the Granular start point, the Grain length, and Record switch of Granular synthesis respectively; index, middle, and ring finger of right hand were used to control the delay volume, the delay time, and the output amount of signal of Feedback respectively. Table 3 shows the mapping of fingers of right hand to various parameters of different sound effectors.

Mode/Right	Finger	Description
Granular synthesis	Index	Granular start
	Middle	Grain length
	Ring	Record switch
Feedback	Index	Delay volume
	Middle	Delay time
	Ring	Signal amount
Reverb	Index	Reverb size
	Middle	Decay time
	Ring	Signal amount

Table 3. Mapping of fingers of right hand to parameters of sound effectors.

4.2 Feet (Shoes)

Feet were used to control the mode switch of sound effectors and mode of 4-channel output via the pressure sensors, which were built on the insoles inside the shoes to detect the weights of feet stepping (ranging from 20g-2kg). The data from detecting was converted into digits by Arduino (ranging from 0 to 1023) and then mapped into parameters via algorithms of Max. When a specific parameter reaches the preset threshold, the mode switch of sound effectors and mode of 4-channel output were triggered; parameters from heel sensor of left and right foot trigger the mode switch of sound effectors; parameters from the forefoot sensor of left foot and heel sensor of right foot trigger the 4-channel sound output mode respectively. Figure 13 shows the mapping of feet to mode and 4-channel output trigger

- ▶ left foot
- ▶ forefoot : 4-channel start
- ▶ heel : mode 1,2,3 trigger
- ▶ right foot
- ▶ forefoot : none
- ▶ heel : mode 1,2,3 trigger

Figure 13. Mapping of feet to mode and 4-channel output trigger.

4.3 Head (Cap)

Head was used to control the sound spatialization via the electric compass (with gyroscope), which was built on the brim of a cap to detect the moving angle of head motion both horizontally and vertically. After converting, the data of horizontal angle (ranging from 0 to 360) was used to control the sound movement among 4 speakers; data of vertical angle was used to decide the decay time of sound

in a speaker. Figure 14 shows mapping of head motion to 4-channel sound spatialization control and decay time of sound (in a speaker).

Figure 14. Mapping of head motion to 4-channel sound spatialization control and decay time of sound (in a speaker).

5. CONCLUSION

At the current stage, the development of Musfit has reached the goal we set: prototyping a wireless integrated wearable interactive music system. However, further studies are needed in order to assess and improve playability and stability of the system, in such a way that Musfit can be effectively employed by performer in concerts.

We hope, in in near future, an optimized version of Musfit could be created, which could not only truly free the performing space of the musician, but also could increase the technological transparency of performance to help audience realize the relationship between music and technology and, as a result, to promote the interests of appreciating an interactive music performance.

Acknowledgments

This research was supported by the Ministry of Science and Technology in Taiwan (R.O.C.). (Project No. 104WFA0650423)

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